

India's Toothless Tobacco Control Law: Implementation of prohibition in educational institutions.

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Abstract:

This commentary is about the compliance and implementation of the tobacco control law in educational institutes or EIs in India. It further discusses a legal case where there was issue of accountability by an EI related to the compliance related to prohibition of tobacco vendors in proximity to the premises. Also discussed are various studies where there is a defiance to the implementation of the law, which sometimes simply includes placing a board prohibiting sale around the EI. The tobacco control law in India must be strengthened so that tobacco, which is a leading cause of preventable diseases, including cancer, can be controlled.

Keywords: *cigarettes, chewable tobacco, pan masala, COTPA Act 2003, New Delhi, Central Information Commission.*

To its credit, India passed the Cigarettes and Other Tobacco Products (Prohibition of Advertisement and Regulation of Trade and Commerce, Production, Supply and Distribution) Act, 2003 or COTPA Act 2003 for short ¹. When the then health minister was speaking on this bill in the parliament, a seasoned politician opposed this by saying raising issues related to the livelihood of tobacco growers and small-scale shopkeepers selling it. Another parliamentarian further inappropriately stated that '*when tobacco is chewed by a person, it protects the teeth, gums and all those things*' and also stated the commercial reasons why tobacco must continue to be grown and sold ². These answers disregard the scientific evidence of the harm which may outdo any possible conjectural benefit. The justification of employment caused by tobacco cannot stand, as the same does not stand for other narcotic drugs ³. With an increasing projection for a rise in cancer cases, especially blamed on the use of tobacco products, India must strengthen and make stricter the tobacco control law ^{4,5}. The same was noted by the parliamentary committee on cancer which put a major focus on tobacco control⁶. The COTPA Act was made in response to the 43rd World Health Assembly, where member states were urged to consider tobacco control strategies, with a focus on protecting children from voluntary exposure to tobacco use and discouraging the use of tobacco ⁷. With the age of tobacco initiation in Indians being reported from 8-15 years, this is all the more crucial ⁸. The COTPA Act considered the early age of initiation by Section 6 of the COTPA Act which dealt with educational institutions where young people spend a large part of their early life. The Section 6 of the COTPA Act 2003 is as follows:

47 *No person shall sell, offer for sale, or permit sale of, cigarette or any other tobacco*
 48 *product- (a) to any person who is under eighteen years of age, and (b) in an area within a*
 49 *radius of one hundred yards of any educational institution.*

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51 This was well intentioned, but its implementation was aimed to be done by outsourcing it to
 52 schools and colleges themselves and decentralising the on-ground enforcement. The
 53 College/School/Headmaster/Principal or even a teacher is an authorised officer to impose and
 54 collect fine against the violation of Section 4 of the COTPA Act 2003, which deals with
 55 prohibition of smoking in all public places including educational institutions ^{1,9}.

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57 Apart from this collection of fines, the schools and colleges were armed with two rather simple
 58 tasks. One, to put a board prohibiting sale of tobacco within tobacco 100 yards of the educational
 59 institution and second to put boards within its premises to prohibit people from using tobacco
 60 within the premises. But the law itself, along with the rules, may be unclear about one important
 61 condition, i.e. the prohibition of sale within 100 yards of the proximity of the educational
 62 institution. Despite the schools and colleges putting up a board to prohibit the sale of tobacco
 63 products within the 100 yards, the responsibility to ensure that there is no presence of tobacco
 64 vendors within this area was unclear, as this was the issue before the Central Information
 65 Commission (No. CIC/ADIMV/C/2023/131421 Order dated 24.10.2024) where a college in Delhi
 66 had, in response to a RTI query, transferred the questions of presence of vendors to the Delhi
 67 Police instead of providing an answer itself ¹⁰. In that matter, it was pleaded by the first author, the
 68 complainant in the matter, that the guidelines by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare clearly
 69 state that *'The educational institution management should ensure that no tobacco products are*
 70 *sold inside the premises and in an area within 100 yards from the premises.*¹¹ The Central
 71 Information Commission in a landmark decision stated that the *'complaint raises significant issue*
 72 *of public interest particularly of a very vulnerable section of the society, i.e., schools and colleges'*
 73 and recommended that proactive measures should be taken by the college in this case.

74 It is to be noted that in multiple studies, such as one in the administrative precincts of New Delhi,
 75 schools did not universally follow the signboard compliance of the COTPA Act ¹². In another
 76 study, the Central Government-run institutions of national importance were checked for their
 77 compliance. National Institutes of Technology or NITs, Indian Institutes of Management or IIMs,
 78 and other such institutions in many cases denied the information regarding compliance to the
 79 COTPA Act 2003. Some of the institutions even went further and bothered to litigated the denial
 80 of information up to a second appeals before the Central Information Commission but did not
 81 arrange for information like instances of fines collected, presence of vendors or even whether
 82 boards have been installed or not ¹³. Similar was the case with central universities in another such
 83 study where there was a lack of compliance¹⁴. In the case of higher educational institutions in
 84 Delhi, the compliance was not universal ¹⁵. Studies, as quoted above, reported cases where
 85 something as simple as installation of boards prohibiting smoking or prohibition of sales around
 86 an educational institutions' proximity (of 100 yards) were not installed.

87 This raises doubts about the well-intentioned objective of the parliament to expect these
 88 educational institutions to enforce the tobacco control law. This is even after the institutions
 89 themselves were empowered to enforce offences and the collecting of fines.

90 The COTPA Act, 2003 must truly be reinvigorated with strict accreditation barriers for educational
 91 institutions which do not comply with the law. Further, even after passage, the COTPA Act 2003

92 has mild punishments as currently the fine for smoking in public places and selling outside of
 93 educational institutions is only two hundred rupees (2-3 \$). This unlikely serves as a deterrent to
 94 translate the intention of discouraging tobacco use. Steps like the amendment of the Juvenile
 95 Justice Act, 2015 which provides for stringent punishment for sale of tobacco products to minors
 96 is in the right direction, but its compliance needs to be evaluated and a focus must be on
 97 strengthening of the one single tobacco law, making it more comprehensive and stricter¹⁶. Recent
 98 directions by the Delhi government for appointment of nodal officers, if not already done as per
 99 law, to oversee compliance of the COTPA Act 2003 in schools are welcome, but these will need
 100 continuous follow up¹⁷. This is all the more important as India, with its large population, must
 101 concentrate on promoting prevention of cancers, about half of which can be prevented, by
 102 controlling risk factors, leading among which is smoking¹⁸.

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